

To Study the Prevalence of Microdeletions of Azfc & Gr/Gr Regions of Y Chromosome in Males with Azoospermia & Oligospermia

Ms. Aarti Agrawal¹, Mr. Nikhil Sanjay Solanki², Ghansham Magar³, Suvarna Magar⁴, Zarina Shaikh⁵, Sanjay Guddetwar⁶, Sandeep Baate⁷

¹Assistant Professor, Medical Biotechnology & Medical Genetics, In-Charge of Genetics Lab, MGM's Medical College & Hospital, Aurangabad

²Tutor, Medical Biotechnology, MGM's Medical College & Hospital, Aurangabad

³Assistant Professor, Dept. of OBGY, IIMSR Medical College, Jalna

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, MGM's Medical College & Hospital, Aurangabad

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Dr. Rafiq Zakaria Centre for Higher Learning and Advanced Research, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India

⁶Assistant Professor, Medical Biochemistry, Principal- MGM School of Biomedical Sciences, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Aurangabad

⁷Assistant Professor, Department of Urology, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Aurangabad

Received: 05-10-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 30-10-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ghansham Magar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Microdeletion of the y chromosome are the second most frequent genetic cause of spermatogenic failure in infertile male after the Klinefelter syndrome. Microdeletions occur in about one in 4000 men in the general population but its frequency is significantly increased among infertile men. The indication for molecular diagnosis of Y chromosome microdeletion is based on sperm concentration and it is strongly advised in patient affected by azoospermia and severe oligozoospermia (<5×106/ML). Microdeletion in the azoospermia factor (AZF): AZFa, AZFb, AZFc Or AZFbc of Y chromosome are clinically relevant and are found in men with severe oligo- or azoospermia. The most frequent deletion type is the AZFc region deletion (~80%) followed by AZFa(0.5-4%), AZFb(1-5%) and AZFbc(1-3%) deletion. Infertility is a global health problem caused by multiple factors and affects approximately 10% to 15% of couples worldwide. The study sought to examine the relationship between male infertility risk and AZFc and gr/gr deletions.

Methodology: The present study was conducted at Department of Genetics of MGM Medical College and Hospital Aurangabad from Oct. 2023 to March 2024 amongst male patients diagnosed with azoospermia or oligospermia within reproductive age, often defined as 18–50 years. In order to test for azoospermia and severe oligozoospermia in humans (men), the EAA/EMQN (2014) guidelines recommend using PCR amplification reagents for two markers on the Y chromosome. This assay provides Y chromosome Microdeletion Detection. - Detection mix sets 1 and 4 are for AZFc-sY254, sY160, sY145, and sY255; gr/gr-sY1291, sY1191; and SRY-sY14 [internal control] is for detection mix set 5.

Result: The highest frequency of AZFc deletions in this study was found in cases of severe oligozoospermia (81%), while AZFa and b deletions were found in azoospermic and oligozoospermic individuals at comparable frequencies. It's interesting to note that compared to the SOAS and oligozoospermic groups (3 and 12%, respectively), the azoospermic group had a higher frequency of double deletions (37%). All of these observations suggest that the severity of the phenotype may be influenced not only by the loci but also by the length of deletion (involving multiple loci). Therefore, it would be clinically relevant to closely monitor and counsel oligospermic patients, particularly those with double deletions, regarding their potential for rapid progression to azoospermia. This information will be required because these patients will require appropriate management and counseling in order to preserve their sperm for use in artificial reproductive technologies (ART).

Conclusion: We discovered that the eight patients we chose for our study fall into the maximum age group of people between the ages of 21 and 40. Male infertility is a multifactorial condition involving a wide range of disorders. Over 30% of male infertility is thought to be caused by abnormalities in sperm production as a result of a genetic defect. Y-Chromosome The discovered AZF gene microdeletions strongly point to spermatogenic failure, irregular sperm concentration, and male factor infertility. The prevalence and implications of YCMs remain highly variable, despite increased awareness among the world's infertile male population.

Keywords: infertility, Y-Chromosome, AZFc, Microdeletion, PCR.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Infertility is a global health problem caused by multiple factors and affects approximately 10% to 15% of couples worldwide [1]. Microdeletion of the y chromosome are the second most frequent genetic cause of spermatogenic failure in infertile male after the Klinefelter syndrome [1]. Microdeletions occur in about one in 4000 men in the general population but its frequency is significantly increased among infertile men [1]. The molecular diagnosis of Y chromosome microdeletion is recommended in the workup of male infertility in men with azoospermia or severe oligozoospermia [1]. Azoospermic men have a higher incidence of microdeletion than oligozoospermic men [2]. The indication for molecular diagnosis of Y chromosome microdeletion is based on sperm concentration and it is strongly advised in patient affected by azoospermia and severe oligozoospermia ($<5 \times 10^6/\text{ML}$) [2]. Microdeletion in the azoospermia factor (AZF): AZFa, AZFb, AZFc Or AZFbc of Y chromosome are clinically relevant and are found in men with severe oligo- or azoospermia [3]. Deletion in this region removes one or more of the candidate genes (DAZ, RBMY, SP9Y and DBY) and cause severe testicular pathology leading to Infertility [4]. The most frequent deletion type is the AZFc region deletion (~80%) followed by AZFa (0.5-4%), AZFb (1-5%) and AZFbc (1-3%) deletion [5]. Deletions which are detected as AZFabc are most likely related to abnormal karyotype such as 46 XX male or iso(Y)[6].

Methodology:

The present study was conducted at Department of Genetics of MGM Medical College and Hospital Aurangabad from Oct. 2023 to March 2024 after ethics committee approval.

Blood samples were collected from the departments of obstetrics, gynecology, and urology. The sample was collected and reported in compliance with all applicable rules and regulations.

Inclusion Criteria: The studies for pooled analysis were chosen based on clear inclusion/exclusion criteria. These were the criteria for inclusion:

1. **Male Patients Diagnosed with Azoospermia or Oligospermia:** Only males with a confirmed diagnosis of azoospermia (absence of sperm in semen) or oligospermia (low sperm count) should be included.

2. **Age Range:** Typically, men within reproductive age, often defined as 18–50 years, are eligible to capture the population most affected by fertility issues.

3. The study sought to examine the relationship between male infertility risk and AZFc and gr/gr deletions;

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients other than azoospermic & oligospermic will be excluded

2. **History of Cryptorchidism or Other Genital Disorders:** Males with a history of cryptorchidism (undescended testicle), testicular trauma, or surgeries impacting testicular function should be excluded, as these factors can independently impact fertility.

3. **Prior Vasectomy or Reproductive Surgery:** Any surgical intervention affecting the reproductive tract can skew the results and should exclude the participant.

Study design and Methodology:

Patients who meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be chosen for the study. The patient's demographic profile, including age, gender, socioeconomic status, etc.

Materials & Methods:

In order to test for azoospermia and severe oligozoospermia in humans (men), the EAA/EMQN (2014) guidelines recommend using PCR amplification reagents for two markers on the Y chromosome. This assay provides Y chromosome Microdeletion Detection. -Detection mix sets 1 and 4 are for AZFc-sY254, sY160, sY145, and sY255; gr/gr-sY1291, sY1191; and SRY-sY14 [internal control] is for detection mix set 5.

Recommended Task Domains

a. The room used to prepare the reagents for the PCR reaction

b. Sample preparation space or room: this is where DNA is extracted from blood samples. The PCR room or area, where gel electrophoresis and heat cyclers are used to perform PCR. Dedicated spaces are advised as part of Good Laboratory Practices (GLP) to prevent cross contamination. Stability of the product and storage conditions the reagent used for DNA extraction needs to be kept at room temperature. The kit's PCR components are stable until the expiration date and should be stored at -15 to -30°C, respectively. It is best to avoid repeatedly thawing and freezing (more than twice), as this could weaken the stability. The reagents should be frozen in aliquots if they will only be used occasionally. Reagents for PCR should be stored between 2 and 8°C for no more than five hours. If the PCR components of the assay are kept at room temperature for an extended amount of time, inaccurate results may be obtained. Repeatedly freezing and thawing without a need will produce unreliable results.

High-quality Frameworks Every lot of DiagoDx

Series TM Y Chromosome Microdeletion Detection is tested against specified standards in compliance

with the ISO-certified Quality Management System (9001-2015) to guarantee consistent product quality.

Table 1: Showing the storage of various reagents

Reagent	Storage
Lysis buffer	RT
BG buffer	RT
W1 buffer	RT
Wash buffer	RT
Elution buffer	RT
BG Columns	RT
Collection tubes	RT
Lysozyme	RT

Table 2: Showing the Components for PCR amplification:

Reagents	Components	Storage
Master mix	Taq polymerase and buffer components	-20C
Detection mix set 1	Primer mix formarkers sY254, sY160, sY145, sY255	-20C
Detection mix set 2	Primer mix for markers sY1291,sY1191	-20C
Detection mix set 3	Primer mix for marker SRY	-20C
Nuclease Free Water		-20C

Nucleic acid extraction procedure:

Genomic DNA extraction offers a quick and easy method for preparing intact, purified DNA from mammalian blood. Its foundation is the specific binding of DNA to a microcentrifuge tube's binding column. Centrifugation with a spin column is a quick way to purify genomic DNA. Wash solution is used to thoroughly wash away impurities. Elution Buffer is then used to elute the genomic DNA. Each purification can process up to 200µl of blood. High-quality genomic DNA has been isolated, and it can be applied to common tasks like PCR analysis, restriction enzyme digestion, and agarose gel analysis. Since ethanol is not used in the purification process, ethanol carryover-related downstream issues are avoided.

Important Guidelines:

Make sure all equipment that comes into contact with DNA, such as pipette tips and micro-centrifuge tubes, is sterile. Maintain a sterile environment to prevent any contamination from DNases. • Make sure no DNases are introduced into the sterile solutions. When processing blood samples, the eluates collected during wash steps contain biohazardous waste.

Complete all centrifugation steps at room temperature to minimize DNA degradation. Avoid repeatedly freezing and thawing DNA samples. Perform lysate preparation steps quickly. The collection tubes and elute should be disposed of as biohazardous waste. Magspin 50(100 preps) protocol:- Processing one female blood sample (extraction control) and one fertile male blood sample (positive control) in addition to your test samples is advised.

Important Note:

1. This system has buffers that are filled with irritants. When handling these buffers, put on a lab coat and gloves.
2. When opening the Wash Buffer for Cat. No. MAGSPIN-50, add 100 ml of ethanol (96–100%).
3. Fill the lysozyme bottle with 5 ml of elution buffer. Before beginning the following steps, please read the important notes.

First Step: RBC Lysis

1. Use an anticoagulant-treat collection tube to gather fresh human blood.
Put 300µl of fresh blood into a 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube (which is not included). Place the sample into a sterile 15 ml centrifuge tube if it exceeds 300 µl (up to 1 ml).
2. Add three times the RBC Lysis Buffer sample volume and mix by inversion. Additionally, add 25µl of lysozyme solution. Avoid vortexing.
3. Let it incubate for ten minutes at room temperature.
4. Centrifuge for five minutes at 3,000 x g to extract all of the supernatant.
5. Use 100 microliters of RBC Lysis Buffer to re-suspend the pellet.

Step 2: Lysis of the Cell

7. Use a vortex mixer to combine 200 µl of BG Buffer.
8. Let the sample lysate sit at room temperature for ten minutes, or until it becomes transparent. Turn the tube over every three minutes while it's incubating.
9. Heat the necessary elution buffer in a water bath at 70oC (for Step 5 DNA elution).

10. (Optional Step): Add 5µl of 10 mg/ml RNase A to the sample and mix by vortexing if RNA-free genomic DNA is needed. After that, incubate at room temperature for five minutes.

Step 3: Attaching

11. Mix the sample with 200µl of ethanol (96–100%) and vortex for 10 seconds. (If there is any precipitate, pipetting.)
12. Attach a 2 ml collection tube to a BG Column. Carefully transfer the sample mixture to the BG Column, making sure to include any precipitate. Discard the 2 ml collection tube after centrifuging for 5 minutes at full speed (14,000 rpm or 10,000 x g). Fill a fresh 2 ml Collection tube with the BG Column.

Step Four: Attaching

11. Mix the sample with 250µl of ethanol (96–100%) and vortex for ten seconds. (If there is any precipitate, pipetting.)
12. Attach a 2 ml collection tube to a BG Column. Move the sample mixture into the BG Column, taking care to include any precipitate. Discard the 2 ml collection tube after centrifuging for 5 minutes at full speed (14,000 rpm or 10,000 x g). Fill a fresh 2 ml Collection tube with the BG Column.

Step 5: Cleaning

13. Use 400µl W1 Buffer to wash the BG Column. Centrifuge at maximum speed for one minute (14,000 rpm or 10,000 x g), then remove the flow-through.
14. Reinstall the BG Column in the tube holding the 2 ml collection. Use 600µl of ethanol-infused wash buffer to clean the BG column. Centrifuge at maximum speed for one minute (14,000 rpm or 10,000 x g), then remove the flow-through. --Upon initial opening, confirm that ethanol has been added to the wash buffer.
15. Reinstall the BG Column in the tube for the 2 ml collection. To dry the column, centrifuge for three more minutes at maximum speed (14,000 rpm or 10,000 x g). --Vital Action! By taking this action, the residual liquid won't hinder any further enzymatic reactions.
16. The dry BG Column should be placed in a fresh 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube in

Step 6- Elution

17. Fill the membrane center of the BG Column with 100µl of either preheated elution buffer or

TE. -- Crucial Action! Make sure the elution solution is dispensed onto the membrane center and absorbed completely for optimal elution.

18. Place the BG Column in an incubator and let it sit at 37°C for ten minutes.
19. To elute the DNA, centrifuge at full speed for one minute (14,000 rpm or 10,000 x g).

--A standard elution volume is 100 µl. Should a greater yield of DNA be needed, carry out the DNA Elution phase once more to enhance DNA recovery; the overall volume could be 200 µl. Step Final: Unadulterated DNA

20. Keep the fragment of DNA at either 4°C or -20°C.

Quantitation of DNA:

Use a fluorometer or UV absorbance at 260 nm to quantify DNA. For PCR, use 25– 100ng of DNA.

Polymerase Chain Reaction-Based Identification of Y Chromosome Micro-Deletions Preparing the Reagent

- When setting up the experiment, keep all of the reagents on the cold rack.
- Defrost frozen reagent aliquots. Steer clear of frequent freeze-thawing.
- After briefly centrifuging them, put them in the cold rack.

Protocol:-

Suggested tests for every PCR run: a) Multiplex primer sets are used to test each sample DNA extract.

b) Controls, both positive and negative:

Female DNA control as negative control; • Fertile/normal male DNA control as Positive Template Control (PTC).

- To check for reagent contamination, use Nuclease Free Water as No Template Control (NTC).

Setup for a reaction

Reaction assay mixes are prepared as a cocktail and then poured into 0.2 ml or 8-tube strip tubes. To account for pipetting error, PTC, and NTC reactions, more master mix

should be made. The relevant test reactions are then supplemented with extracted nucleic acid and controls.

Prepare and run the PCR reaction plate

Table 3: Showing the Preparation of PCR master mixes according to the table below for each sample:

Reagent	AZFc (1X)	gr/gr (1X)	SRY (1X)
Mastermix	10 µL	10 µL	10 µL
Primer Mix	1 µL	2 µL	1 µL
d/w	8 µ	7 µL	8 µ
DNA	1 µL	1 µL	1 µL
Total Volume	20 µL	20 µL	20 µL

1. Prior to initiating the reaction, all reagents need to be thawed, vortexed, and centrifuged and kept on a cold rack.
2. In addition to the sample(s) to be tested, controls for each of the five reaction sets should include a female DNA control, a male control, and water (NTC).
3. Water ought to be free of nucleases.
4. Create the three PCR master mixes (gr/gr, AZFc, and SRY) in accordance with the instructions given below.
5. Divide the 19 µL of the master mix cocktails into separate 0.2 ml PCR tubes or PCR strips by gently vortexing them.
6. Before setting up the female and fertile male controls, first set up the NTC. It is best to add the test samples last.
7. Close the tubes, vortex them briefly, and centrifuge them for 20 seconds.
8. Proceed with the PCR run using the below-listed thermal cycling parameters.

Set up the experiment –

Table 4: Showing the Thermal Cycling Parameters:

Step	Temperature	Time (min)	Stage
Initial activation	95°C	05:00	Hold
Denaturation	95°C	00:30	Cycling (35 cycles)
Annealing	56°C	02:00	
Extension	72°C	00:30	
Final Extension	72 °C	05:00	Hold
Final Hold	4 °C	∞	Hold

After PCR run, proceed for gel analysis or store PCR products at 4 °C. For prolonged storage, store at -20 °C.

Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

1. Prepare a 4% agarose gel in 1X TAE buffer containing 0.5µg/ml ethidium bromide for the best possible visualization of the amplification products.
2. Because loading dye has already been added to the blue master mix, pour the entire amplified product into the prepared gel's well.
3. Fill each gel with 5µl of the 100bpDNA ladder.
4. Run the gel at 5V/cm (the voltage across the electrodes) in 1X TAE buffer.
5. Use a gel imager or UV transilluminator to take pictures of the gel.

Analysis of results and interpretation Controls:

1. Fertile Male Genomic DNA Control: This

reaction serves as a positive control and, as the table below illustrates, should demonstrate amplification for every target in the multiplex master mix. The test ought to be deemed invalid and redone if any of the anticipated amplification products are absent from the reactions using the fertile male DNA control.

No template control (NTC): NTC serves as reagent control and shouldn't cause any target to amplify. DNA contamination is indicated by amplification products in NTC. In this instance, it would be best to repeat the experiment using new reagents and taking the necessary safety measures to prevent contamination.

Experimental Sample:

- 1) Check each sample to see if the predicted PCR products are present or absent if the above control criteria are met. The existence of a micro-deletion of the sequence is indicated by the lack of PCR products for particular Y chromosome regions.

Table 5: Showing the PCR Amplification Product Outline

Detection mix set 1	Re-gion	Expected band size (bp)	Fertile Male DNA	Detection mix set 2	Re-gion	Expected band size (bp)	Fertile Male DNA
sY254	AZFc	280	+	sY1291	gr/gr	527	+
sY160	AZFc	236	+	sY14	gr/gr	385	+

sY145	AZFc	143	+	sY1191			
sY255	AZFc	126	+				
Detection mix set	Re-gion	Expected band size (bp)	Fertile Male DNA				
sY14	SRY	470	+				

Lane 1- NTC for AZFc set

Lane 2 - Fertile male for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp] Lane 3 - NTC for gr/gr set

Lane 4 – Fertile male for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]

Sample size: We will collect all cases of YCMD within time frame of 6 months.

Statistical Analysis:

Microsoft Excel will be used to enter the data, and

SPSS version 24.0th will be used for analysis. For quantitative variables, the mean and standard deviation will be computed, while proportions will be computed for categorical variables. Additionally, data will be displayed visually in the form of tables, graphs, and bar diagrams, among other formats. The mean and standard deviation will be used to represent quantitative data. P-values will be examined at significance levels of 5%.

Confidential

Observations and Result

Observation-

Lane 1 - NTC for AZFc set

Lane 2 – Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp]

Lane 3 - Fertile male for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp] Lane 4 - Contain 100 base pair ladder

Lane 5 - NTC for gr/gr set

Lane 6 –Patient sample for gr/gr set [Presence of 2

bands i.e. 527, 385 bp] Lane 7 – Fertile male for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]

Interpretation-

The patient no. 1 is negative for both AZFc & gr/gr regions.

Observation-

Lane 1 – Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp]

Lane 2 - Fertile male for AZFc set [Presence of 4

bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp] Lane 3 - NTC for AZFc set

Lane 4 - Contain 100 base pair ladder

Lane 6 -- Fertile male for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp] Lane 6 -Patient sample for

gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]

Interpretation-

The patient no. 2 & 3 are negative for both AZFc & gr/gr regions.

Observation-

Lane 1 - NTC for gr/gr set.

Lane 2 -Patient sample for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]. Lane 3 -Patient sample for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]. Lane 4 -Patient sample for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands

i.e. 527, 385 bp]. Lane 5 - Contain 100 base pair ladder.

Interpretation-

The patient no.4,5,&6 are negative for gr/gr region.

Observation-

Lane 1 - Contain 100 base pair ladder
 Lane 2 - Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp]
 Lane 3 - Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp]
 Lane 4 - Positive control for AZFc set [Presence of

3 bands i.e. 380, 143, 126 bp & Absence of 1 band i.e. 236 bp]
 Lane 5 - Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp] Lane 6 - NTC for AZFc set

Interpretation-

The patient no.4, 5 & 6 are negative for AZFc region.

Observation-

Lane 1 - NTC for AZFc set

Lane 2 - Fertile male for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp]

Lane 3 – Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 3 bands i.e. 380, 143, 126 bp & Absence of 1 band i.e. 236 bp]

This patient is positive for SY160 (236). (PATIENT NO.7).

Lane 4 - Patient sample for AZFc set [Presence of 4 bands i.e. 380, 236, 143, 126 bp] Lane 5 - Contain 100 base pair ladder

Interpretation-

The patient no.8 is negative for AZFc region. The patient no.7 is **positive** for AZFc region.

Observation-

Lane 1 - NTC for gr/gr set.

Lane 2 –Fertile male for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]. Lane 3 –Patient sample for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands i.e. 527, 385 bp]. Lane 4 –Patient sample for gr/gr set [Presence of 2 bands

i.e. 527, 385 bp]. Lane 5 - Contain 100 base pair ladder.

Interpretation-

The patient no.7&8 are negative for gr/gr region.

Medical condition of Patients

Religion wise distribution of patients

Occupation wise distribution of patient

Discussion:

This study was conducted in MGM Medical College & hospital, to study the prevalence of microdeletions of AZFc & gr/gr regions of Y chromosome in males with Azoospermia & Oligospermia.

It has generally been proposed that azoospermia is linked to deletions of AZFa and b, while oligozoospermia is linked to deletions of AZFc. The highest frequency of AZFc deletions in this study was found in cases of severe oligozoospermia (81%), while AZFa and b deletions were found in azoospermic and oligozoospermic individuals at comparable frequencies. It's interesting to note that compared to the SOAS and oligozoospermic groups (3 and 12%, respectively), the azoospermic group had a higher frequency of double deletions (37%).

All of these observations suggest that the severity of the phenotype may be influenced not only by the loci but also by the length of deletion (involving multiple loci). It is well known that Yq deletion-carrying oligozoospermic individuals eventually develop azoospermia. Therefore, it would be clinically relevant to closely monitor and counsel oligospermic patients, particularly those with double deletions, regarding their potential for rapid progression to azoospermia. This information will be required because these patients will require appropriate management and counseling in order to preserve their sperm for use in artificial reproductive technologies (ART).

In the present study objectives were,

- 1) To determine the cause of male infertility in non-obstructive azoospermia and moderate to severe oligospermia.
- 2) To find out the most frequent deletion type AZFc & gr/gr region deletion. Total 8 patients diagnosed for Y chromosome microdeletion was studied.

Age of patients:

The age group of patients between the ages of 21 and 40 has the largest range in the data distribution, or 8 patients.

Occupation of Patients:

Private employees make up the majority of patients—50%—followed by business owners (25%), government workers (0%), workers (12.5%), unemployed people (12.5%), and farmers (0%).

Religion of patients:

It can detect that the majority of its patients—62% of them Hindu—and 38% of them Muslim.

Residential area of patients:

According to the above chart, the greatest percentage of patients—75.5%—dwell in urban areas as opposed to rural ones—24.4%.

Awareness of Infertility:

It can clearly be observed in the stated graph that almost all patients had heard about Infertility.

Summary & Conclusion

This study investigated the prevalence of azoospermic and oligospermic patients through experimentation. We found that the maximum age group of the 8 patients we targeted for our study belongs to those between the ages of 21 and 40. A broad range of disorders are involved in the multifactorial condition of male infertility. It has been estimated that abnormalities related to sperm production resulting from a genetic defect account for over 30% of male infertility. Y-Chromosome the AZF gene microdeletions that have been found are strongly suggestive of male factor infertility, irregular sperm concentration, and spermatogenic failure. Although the world's infertile male population is becoming more aware of YCMs, the actual prevalence and ramifications of these

rearrangements are still very variable. Through experimentation, this study examined the prevalence of azoospermic and oligospermic patients. We discovered that the eight patients we chose for our study fall into the maximum age group of people between the ages of 21 and 40. Male infertility is a multifactorial condition involving a wide range of disorders. Over 30% of male infertility is thought to be caused by abnormalities in sperm production as a result of a genetic defect. Y-Chromosome The discovered AZF gene microdeletions strongly point to spermatogenic failure, irregular sperm concentration, and male factor infertility. The prevalence and implications of YCMs remain highly variable, despite increased awareness among the world's infertile male population.

Limitations of Study

Other investigations are necessary to validate the findings of this study because the sample population was small. Other measures that can be taken for prevention is repetitive counseling of patients towards a healthy lifestyle. Camps should be organized by government or private sectors at different locations to educate people about Infertility and to provide free health checkups related to infertility. Dietitians can be appointed for providing proper diet plans to the patients who are likely to face Infertility.

The likely reasons of developing Infertility and reasons to be more prone is poor lifestyle of the patients. Their negligence over obesity and sedentary

lifestyle, consumption of nicotine-containing products, taking an unhealthy diet, not exercising on a regular basis, irregular in taking proper medicines, carelessness over regular medical health checkup, and not following proper instructions given by the physician.

References:

1. Stacy Colaco & Deepak Modi (2019) Consequences of Y chromosome microdeletions beyond male infertility. *Journal of Assisted Reproduction and Genetics*.36,1329–1337 .
2. Rani, D.S., Rajender, S., Pavani, K. et al. High frequencies of Non-Allelic Homologous Recombination (NAHR) events at the AZF loci and male infertility risk in Indian men. *Sci Rep* 9,6276 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-019-019-0>
3. C. Krausz et al 2013EAA/EMQN best practice guidelines for molecular diagnosis of Y- chromosomal microdeletions: state-of-the-art 2013. *Andrology*, 2014, 2, 5-19
4. Skaletsky, H. et al. (2003) The male-specific region of the human Y chromosome is a mosaic of discrete sequence classes. *Nature* 423, 8 25–37.
5. Vollrath, D. et al. (1992) The human Y chromosome: A 43-interval map based on naturally occurring deletions. *Science* 258, 52–9.
6. Singh A, Agarwal A. The role of sperm chromatin integrity and DNA damage on male infertility. *Open Reprod Sci J* 2011; 3: 65–71.